

DIGITAL PLATAFORMAS AS RESOURCES TO ENGLISH LANGUAGE TEACHING

PLATAFORMAS DIGITALES COMO RECURSOS PARA LA ENSEÑANZA DEL INGLÉS

PLATAFORMAS DIGITAIS COMO RECURSOS PARA O ENSINO DE LÍNGUA INGLESA

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Abstract

The Common National Curriculum Base defends the use of diverse materials to meet students' different needs. Due to the pandemic, educational professionals were obligated to use digital platforms to adapt their methodologies to remote teaching and the student's social situations. However, online classes do not offer the same interactions that in-person classes do, making the learning and the relationship less attractive, and not being able to captivate students' attention. This way, the research has objectives to present the digital platforms as resources to stimulate and differentiate English teaching in a remote context, to reflect on the English language learning-teaching in remote classes, to comprehend what is the importance of the platform and digital literacy, and finally, to analyze the use of digital technologies in remote classes, evidencing the pros and cons. As a methodology, bibliographic research was developed with an exploratory approach where other productions were observed discussing the use of digital tools in English teaching. Therefore, the results were presented from qualitative data analysis. For theoretical contribution, it was used the works of Oliveira *et al* (2022), Segaty;Bailer (2020), and Belém;Guimarães (2020) that covers the inclusion of technology in the English learning context. The research has as results the use of digital platforms as interactive resources to apply in the teaching, offering a more complete, interactive, and sufficient class to students' comprehension of the subject covered.

Keywords: Education; Teaching by Multimedia; Influence of Multimedia; Teaching Means; Educational Technology.

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Resumen

La Base Curricular Común Nacional aboga el uso de materiales variados para satisfacer las distintas necesidades de los alumnos. Debido al contexto pandémico, los profesionales de la educación se han visto obligados a utilizar plataformas digitales para adaptar sus metodologías a la enseñanza a distancia y a la situación social del alumno. Sin embargo, las clases en línea no ofrecen las mismas interacciones que las clases presenciales, por lo que el aprendizaje y las relaciones resultan menos atractivos y no cautivan la atención de los estudiantes. Así, la investigación presenta las plataformas digitales como recursos para agilizar y diferenciar la enseñanza del inglés en un contexto a distancia, además de reflexionar sobre la enseñanza y el aprendizaje del inglés en clases a distancia, comprender la importancia de las plataformas y la alfabetización digital y, por último, analizar el uso de las tecnologías digitales en las clases a distancia, destacando sus ventajas e inconvenientes. La metodología utilizada fue la investigación bibliográfica con enfoque exploratorio, que buscó otros trabajos que discuten el uso de herramientas digitales en la enseñanza del inglés. Los resultados se presentaron mediante análisis cualitativo de datos. Como apoyo teórico, se utilizaron Oliveira et al (2022), Segaty; Bailer (2020) y Belém; Guimarães (2020), que abordan la inserción de las tecnologías en el contexto educativo de la lengua inglesa. La investigación ha dado como resultado el uso de las plataformas digitales como recursos interactivos para la enseñanza, proporcionando una lección más interactiva para que los alumnos comprendan los contenidos tratados.

Palabras clave: Educación; Enseñanza Multimedia; Influencia de los Multimedia; Medios de Enseñanza; Tecnología Educativa.

Resumo

A Base Nacional Comum Curricular (BNCC) defende a utilização de materiais variados para alcançar as diferentes necessidades dos alunos. Devido ao contexto pandêmico, os profissionais da educação foram obrigados a utilizar plataformas digitais para adequar suas metodologias ao ensino remoto e à situação social do aluno. Porém, as aulas *on-line* não oferecem as mesmas interações que as aulas presenciais, deixando a aprendizagem e as relações menos atraentes, não cativando a atenção dos alunos. Dessa forma, a pesquisa tem como objetivos apresentar as plataformas digitais como recursos para dinamizar e diferenciar o ensino de Língua Inglesa em um contexto remoto, além de refletir sobre o ensino aprendizagem da Língua Inglesa em aulas remotas, compreender qual a importância das plataformas e do letramento digital e por fim analisar o uso das tecnologias digitais em aulas remotas, evidenciando suas vantagens e desvantagens. Como metodologia, foi desenvolvido um trabalho de pesquisa bibliográfica com uma abordagem exploratória, onde foram observadas outras produções que discutem o uso de ferramentas digitais no ensino da Língua Inglesa. Portanto, os resultados foram apresentados a partir de uma análise de dados qualitativa. Para aporte teórico, foram utilizados os trabalhos de Oliveira *et al* (2022), Segaty; Bailer (2020) e Belém;Guimarães (2020) que abrangem a inserção das tecnologias no contexto educacional da Língua Inglesa. A pesquisa possui como resultado o uso das plataformas digitais como recursos interativos para empregar no ensino, proporcionando uma aula mais completa, interativa e suficiente para a compreensão dos alunos a respeito do conteúdo abordado.

Palavras-chaves: Educação; Ensino por Multimeios; Influência dos Multimeios; Meios de Ensino; Tecnologia Educacional.

Introduction

In 2020, the teaching methodologies and the means of interaction between teachers and students were completely remodeled due to the Covid-19 pandemic, which resulted in an extensive period of isolation around the world. Consequently, it was not possible to attend the school environment in person, so the actions that used to be performed physically were then performed in the *online* universe, including the application of classes in basic education and higher education. For such changes to occur, Emergency Remote Learning (ERL) was applied, and face-to-face activities were transferred to the digital medium (FAIER, 2021).

Hence, the institutions, their teachers and students had to adapt to the context and the new classroom, exploring the means of communication and the technologies that were at their disposal to achieve their goals effectively. However, due to the global situation and sometimes because of lack of resources or interest, some teachers kept their classes similar to how they were in the face-to-face model, neither changing nor experimenting with new elements (SEGATY; BAILER, 2021).

As much as the ERL is an emergency adaptation of the face-to-face modality, the use of the term "adaptation" implies an adjustment of the element adapted to the context in which it fits at the moment (DICIO, 2022), i.e., in the case presented, it is the adjustment of teaching to the digital context. Therefore, due to several different reasons, but with emphasis in this research, and to this lack of adjustments in the remote model, students suffered with loss of motivation, interaction, and active learning (OLIVEIRA *et al*, 2022; OLIVEIRA, 2021) mainly in the teaching of English Language, which needs communication and contact with the language for content retention.

In ERL, the English Language subject has an even more reduced workload, so as not to keep the student in constant contact with technological devices screens, (DIRGRAD, 2021) and due to the inconveniences provided by an emergency remote education, the subject loses the social factor that is inherent to the study of a language, since the interaction becomes subsidized by devices, without a direct relationship with the learner who will still suffer with the abrupt change of school environment, resulting in the losses already mentioned.

That said, how can teachers promote a differentiated and stimulating teaching and learning of the English Language in a remote context? From this question, this research is guided to the hypothesis that the effective use of digital platforms as resources to apply in teaching can provide a diversified class, because they already have a great importance in the period of ERL and present ample materials and teaching resources that can be applied in the teaching of English Language aiming an improvement of the class, of its activities and of its administration (OLIVEIRA *et al*, 2022), besides being always present in the daily life of new generations and becoming increasingly necessary for older generations as well.

Consequently, the use of the platforms includes learning how to use them effectively, that is, the digital literacy of the teachers, and even of the students, is also an indispensable factor to achieve a dynamic and attractive lesson in the digital model.

Thus, this research aims to reflect on the teaching and learning of the English Language in remote context, to understand the importance of platforms and digital literacy and to analyze the use of digital technologies in remote classes, highlighting their advantages and disadvantages. The work was developed within the framework of Applied Linguistics, from bibliographic research with an exploratory approach, as we observed other productions that discuss the use of digital tools in English Language teaching and in remote teaching. Moreover, we emphasize that the analyzed tools were also part of our journey in the Languages and Literatures course in the pandemic period and in the face-to-face return.

The article brought, therefore, qualitative results about the theme and has as main theoretical contributions the researches of Segaty and Bailer (2020), Belém and Guimarães (2020) and Oliveira *et al* (2022) about the use of digital tools in the remote educational context of the English Language. As a result, digital platforms were presented as resources to dynamize and differentiate the teaching of English Language in a remote context.

Remote Teaching and the English Language: reflections

Emergency Remote Learning (ERE) was adopted due to the restriction measures against the spread of the Covid-19 pandemic in 2020 and is characterized as an adaptation of face-to-face teaching to the temporary technological environment, while it was not possible to conduct the activities face-to-face, with a reduced timetable and activities in synchronous and asynchronous formats (DIRGRAD, 2021). Thus, it was necessary to use technological means to make the schools' schedule effective, forcing teachers to quickly learn how to manage the use of video call platforms for the meetings and of applications for sending messages and files for the materials and activities of each subject, as well as students also had to become familiar with the platforms chosen by the institution.

However, as necessary as the application of ERL was, this type of teaching was not very effective for the students and teachers who were forced to adopt it. According to Faier (2021, p. 05), "it is possible to perceive flaws in activities that promote the interaction of teachers with students and of students with their peers in pedagogical practices performed remotely". The teachers did not have much time to become acquainted with the digital environment that they would need to work during the isolation. They had to modify their way of teaching and their planning according to a platform that they did not have much knowledge in order to continue the classes. With this, some classes and activities were not suitable for the intended format. Segaty and Bailer (2020) state that:

³[...] more than ever, the basic education teachers of the 21st century needed to reinvent himself so quickly that there was no time to ponder what they were doing [...] but the challenge lies in the fact that many education professionals hardly take any notice of what is being produced on their behalf, or simply, for different reasons, remain in their comfort zone and refuse to innovate. (p.263)

The lack of knowledge, time, and even interest about the platforms used and their potential were the main reasons for teachers to offer the same classes taught face-to-face in the digital format, agreeing with the authors Segaty and Bailer (2020, p. 265) when they again state that "when they do not have much idea of what is expected, people tend to replicate what they know and are used to doing". In other

³ All quotes were translated by the authors.

words, teachers applied the same knowledge of face-to-face methodologies in remote classes, ignoring the new context in which the classes were based and focusing only on how they would be transmitted to the students, following the rules of the institution.

This lack of knowledge and the little exploration of technology in a positive way is a result of the lack of structure of schools that do not have enough technological apparatus to be used by teachers or that, even though they have some technological resources, do not encourage their professionals to use them.

By including these initial reflections on ERL to English Language teaching, students and teachers lose the interaction and social factor that is dominant in the teaching of a new language. Miccoli (2007, apud Oliveira et al, 2022) says that the English language is contextual "because its teaching is strongly marked by the support of society and institution". By teaching an entirely virtual class, without the necessary changes and social interaction, the study of English Language does not address the intercultural perspective which is fundamental to language acquisition.

Therefore, it is noticeable that the lack of knowledge of the educational professional regarding the effective use of technologies for the remote teaching of English Language is one of the main factors for an inadequate approach of the classes in the pandemic context. In the next session, the importance of digital literacy and the appropriate use of the available platforms will be addressed.

The relevance of literacy and digital platforms

One of the problems of the remote teaching of English was the inadequate use of digital platforms due to the lack of knowledge of education professionals about them. Therefore, it is necessary to equip teachers with the technologies chosen by the educational institution to be used in periods of ERL, in addition to encouraging the professional to make more use of the potential and tools of these platforms, because:

the teacher who researches and always seeks to be updated and work on what best fits his students can reap good rewards, even in times of uncertainty, when everyone is trying to do their best to learn and adapt their pedagogical work (SEGATY; BAILER, 2021, p. 269)

As much as the scenario was not ideal, in the realm of teaching, it served to challenge those teachers who choose to stay in their comfort zone and to teach those who were open to change, because this is a primary function of the education professional, to seek to adapt their knowledge to unimaginable situations and contexts, whether in their relationship with students or in the context in which they need to work.

Digital Literacy is defined by Silva (2012) as:

[...] to know how to search, select, use the various tools available to fulfill various purposes; it is to relate to their peers, constantly learn, build, transform, rebuild, exercise authorship, share knowledge, etc., always using the resources of the Web, either for personal or professional life. And, in the specific case of teachers, whether for face-to-face classes, distance learning, or a hybridization between these two possibilities. (p. 04)

Therefore, this skill is characterized in using technological resources critically in the pedagogical process, reflecting if it should be used in a specific situation, how it can be used in a best manner and why. The Digital Literacy of teachers, then, is important nowadays to meet the demands of the evolution of technology in society due to the greater accessibility of the Internet and digital platforms, including students in this evolution, through modernized classes that can achieve a better competence.

Therefore, "it becomes necessary to prepare the educator to adopt new responsibilities as a mediator in the process of obtaining information and increasing the creativity of their students" (BELÉM; GUIMARÃES, 2020, p. 02). To achieve a good level of Digital Literacy, school and educational institutions must promote an effective training of professionals in the platforms chosen for remote learning and the most known resources to stimulate teachers to seek this new capacity, so that they can explore this universe with their students.

Realizing the relevance of Digital Literacy in the field of education, the role of digital platforms within the virtual or non-virtual classroom is also evident. Digital platforms are applications, websites, programs, technological and digital environments that can provide an aid to those who use them for various purposes. In ERL, the platforms were essential to the interactions between teachers, students, and institutions, as they were able to provide the necessary subsidy to continue with the classes.

In the English Language, "the quantity and variety of resources, as well as the ease of access and communication enrich the quality of interaction and learning" (SANTOS, 2009, p. 116 apud BELÉM; GUIMARÃES, 2020, p. 02). The platforms have several materials available and most of them in English language, so the student learns the target language from the experience of use, practice, and research and from a content that is meaningful to him, making them feel more excited and motivated with the themes worked.

By taking advantage of the predominant visual side of the platforms, the teacher instigates an entertaining look of the content, applying it as a strategy to make learning more attractive and stimulating for students. As Lima and Fernandes (2019) prove in their experience report by stating that:

The willingness of these students was visibly greater when we used technological devices that called attention to the visual, to observation, to sound, among other possible resources. In addition to being clearly more engaged, we received encouraging feedback from the students themselves. (p. 28)

Herewith, we can understand that the application of digital platforms, besides being necessary to provide a means of communication, is also important to build an attractive and dynamic class for students, stimulating them to participate and be interested in the subject, given their variety of functions and their variety of content and formats that serve as sources of research, practice, and creativity for students and teachers. For having these characteristics, the tools can and should be used in the virtual and face-to-face classroom. In the specific teaching of the English Language, the platforms play important roles since the teaching of this subject "demands the incorporation of information and communication technology tools, to become more dynamic, innovative and more interesting to students of basic education" (OLIVEIRA et al, 2022, p. 06).

Thus, information and communication technologies are great allies in the teaching-learning process, but it requires qualified teachers/mediators capable of using them effectively to achieve the desired objectives. (SILVA; ALVES; FERNANDES, 2021, p. 08)

Thus, for the application of digital platforms to occur, using the most of their characteristics and potential, not only as a support for communication, it is essential that the Digital Literacy of teachers is efficient, so that the professionals themselves can present activities that require the implementation of these platforms, as happened in the ERL, making the students also learn to handle them according to the demand, besides stimulating them to collaborate with a more dynamic class.

In the next unit, some digital platforms will be analyzed, by checking their advantages and disadvantages according to what has been said about their importance for English language teaching.

Digital Platforms: advantages and disadvantages

To begin analyzing the digital platforms, it is necessary to define which ones were chosen for this study. The criterion used to determine these platforms was that they were cited in the papers used for the research and were used for personal experience with remote teaching of English or as virtual material, and the following were selected: YouTube, Padlet, Word Wall and Google Forms.

The points analyzed for each platform individually will be: 1) Description of the platform; 2) Relevance for English language teaching; 3) Advantages and disadvantages of its use.

Starting with YouTube, which can be defined as an online video platform under Google. YouTube uses audiovisual content, in which it is possible for its users to watch and post videos and give feedback to other users' videos through comments and likes. The platform has videos with various types of content, (educational, interactive, entertainment, personal) being posted by professionals in the field or not (SILVA; CARVALHO JUNIOR, 2020).

And in its latest updates, YouTube added the Shorts mode, with shorter videos and vertical model for users who are used to the presentation of content in faster models, consuming more in less time.

YouTube presents relevance to the teaching of English Language from the fact that "allows students to learn through materials that are meaningful to them (videos, music, movies, etc.)" (SILVA; CARVALHO JÚNIOR, 2020, p. 140), besides presenting diverse educational content about the English Language or with the English Language in use.

Thus, "this platform and its great variety of content can motivate students to explore the wide range of material in search of new information" (SILVA; CARVALHO JÚNIOR, 2020, p. 134). Students can also be youtubers, as those who post on the platform are called, by posting presentations about the English Language, facilitating the teacher's evaluation in a digital way.

This platform's main advantages are the incredible amount of content on various topics in different languages, which can be used by teachers or can be used to instigate students to research and analyze sources. Equally advantageous is the fact that it is a platform that interacts with audiovisual, not only with text, exercising listening skills, "oral and written comprehension and production, as well as specific aspects of language, such as vocabulary, pronunciation, and grammar" (WATKINS; WILLKINS, 2011, KABOCHA; ELYAS, 2018, AZEVEDO; MATIAS, 2019, apud KOBBS; BETTONI, 2022).

The platform also provides an attractive environment "because it is a resource that refers to distraction and fun, (and) may be understood by students as a pedagogical proposal that arouses the interest in learning" (BALADELI; ALTOÉ, 2009 apud BELÉM; GUIMARÃES, 2020). However, as disadvantages, the platform presents not so reliable sources, since anyone can post videos on the tool, thus presenting content that is not appropriate for students.

Also due to its vast catalog, students can get distracted by the variety provided and the information-filled interface that the site presents. In addition to the fact that students may use the platform to search for ready answers to activities requested by the teacher, without critiquing the content they are consuming for the situation.

Therefore, it is the institution's responsibility to provide the appropriate digital literacy for the education professional to exercise the responsibility of guiding the student on how to use the platform in an appropriate and critical manner to what was requested and for his personal use, knowing how to differentiate its objectives.

In relation to Padlet, the platform is a site and application that provides a kind of wall, where the user can post photos, videos, links, texts, and other media to other users who have the link to the post and can be used and handled by several users in a single wall. The tool also has a space for comments, where users can interact and provide feedback on the posts. The platform is relevant for English language teaching, because "the written skill in English language can be improved with the collaboration among students, through the interactive online tool Padlet" (CARVALHO et al, 2020, p. 167 - 168).

Therefore, the main advantage of the tool is the use of a collaborative environment for students to practice writing and even reading in English, because students can read the comments of their classmates and open a discussion, or learn new words, get inspired by other texts, thus learning within a social connection.

The proposal of feedback in the comments is also an interesting factor of the platform, motivating students to improve and feel more confident with their posts. Padlet can also be used as a complement to what has been studied or with themes outside those discussed in class, motivating students to participate in activities outside the school context. By being able to take advantage of different media elements, Padlet also awakens students' creativity in how they can present the text, exemplifying the discussion with images, gifs, citing a song, etc.

The platform also provides an environment in which students can actively communicate with each other and with the teacher who follows the process in a passive way, letting students create their own learning. According to Carvalho et al (2020, p. 168) "the use of the Padlet platform [...] was well accepted by the students and [...] the use of the tool in the form of a mural contributed as an aid to creativity, writing, and vocabulary learning".

As a disadvantage we can mention more superficial factors that can be improved, such as the possibility of students not knowing how to use the application; students posting their texts in anonymous templates, making it difficult for the teacher to identify them; the student's technological support, such as their internet connection; and students being afraid to write in another language on an online platform where everyone in the class can read. Realizing how few disadvantages there are to using Padlet in English Language education, it is feasible to use it as an effective resource to motivate students and instigate their creativity.

The WordWall platform is a site that creates and makes available several educational and interactive games. There, the teacher can create a game from existing templates, or download games created and shared by other teachers. The site has the option of online activities or printed activities, making it possible to use the interactive games remotely or face-to-face. The games can be played individually or in groups, with scoring options, timer, lives, and models to be customized according to the preference and needs of the educational professional (PEREIRA FILHO; FRANCO, 2021).

WordWall is relevant in teaching the English Language by presenting interactive activities for students to learn in a fun way and through a real and natural experience. Teachers can use the platform "to review content, assimilate concepts, improve vocabulary, among many other learning tools" (PEREIRA FILHO; FRANCO, 2021, p. 11). With this, it is possible to learn and teach various contents through a single platform, since it is versatile to meet the objectives of the class, whether it is to practice vocabulary, grammar, translation or even start debates on important topics of the English Language.

The main advantage of WordWall is its variety of templates that can fit almost any content that the teacher needs to explain previously, review, assign concepts, use as a homework activity or interactive game. Thus, the teacher can adapt classroom activities to interactive models and also adapt content and exercises to the taste or needs of each class.

Other advantages are the media presentations, which help visual learners learn and train students' assimilation of meanings. "Therefore, we emphasize the importance of the tool that is presented in a simple and intuitive way, allowing the creation of educational games in a very fast way" (PEREIRA FILHO; FRANCO, 2021, p. 35099).

The main disadvantage is the restricted use in the free form, the possibility of not finding an activity you want, not being able to adapt to the games presented or use models that are not suitable for the type of lesson taught. Thus, digital literacy is necessary for the professional to be able to use this platform in a complete and compatible way with its purposes.

Finally, Google Forms is another Google platform, in which any user who has Google's email can use it. It has as its main purpose the creation of online survey forms. From this idea the platform provides elements to develop other types of research, such as collecting data from people interested in job openings, social work, event registration, participation in university programs and especially the preparation of tests and activities in the remote educational environment (LEMOS, 2022).

Google Forms presents a great relevance for English language teaching precisely because it is a tool for creating data collection, so from it the teacher can collect the students' knowledge about the subject or develop a more traditional activity, although interactive, to evaluate the students' answers. It can also be used to receive feedback from students, to suggest topics and dynamics, countless purposes that have the same goal of collecting information about something. The platform also provides direct contact with English through questions written in the target language that require answers in the same language, instigating the student to practice reading and writing skills.

As an advantage, Google Forms has the same versatility as WordWall for creating activities, being able to add media and links that incorporate more context to the practice. The interface of the tool is very intuitive, which helps the student to have a more autonomous learning, without the need for very strict guidelines. The platform's environment resembles the traditional printed activities, tests and notebooks used in the face-to-face model, but adapted to the digital model with improvements and increments, which makes the student more familiar with the site, but without leaving the dynamic aspect aside.

By knowing how to use this resource well, it is possible to apply a contextualized, interactive, and dynamic practice through the elements provided by the platform itself, and even to use several platforms within it, "enabling the elaboration of a dynamic, autonomous, and interactive activity, even if the students were interacting remotely" (LEMOS, 2022, p. 206).

One of the disadvantages of technology, however, is the poor appropriateness of its use. The fact that it looks a bit more like the traditional, can lead the teacher to apply traditional activities of questions and answers without exploring the potential of the tool that is at their disposal with countless possibilities. The fact that it is very autonomous can also be bad for the student, not interacting much with classmates and with the teacher, who thus focuses only on the answers on the form, without knowing how the student develops his mindset to answer them, and without being able to provide closer monitoring.

When analyzing the platforms, it is remarkable what they have in common. They all have the insertion of different media, multifunctionality, the use of feedback, and the need for interaction among users. So, we conclude that these are some of the elements necessary to provide dynamic, interactive, and enhanced activities in digital teaching, but that they can also be applied to face-to-face teaching. And to achieve these elements, it is important that professionals have mastery over the tools that are at their disposal.

Therefore, it is clear that Digital Literacy is extremely necessary to develop appropriate activities for the digital context of remote and even face-to-face classes. It is also noticeable that the technologies mentioned in this unit have more advantages than disadvantages in their use, thus being satisfactory resources to make the teaching of English Language in a remote context more attractive.

Concluding remarks

Considering all that has been exposed in this article, it is possible to understand that the remote teaching of English Language was not useful for students due to the emergency in which it was applied, pressuring teachers to use only what they already knew in the classroom. Thus, the professionals, for various

reasons, could not prepare themselves properly for digital teaching, and continued with their traditional classes, without adapting what was necessary to make the teaching more dynamic and to motivate the students. Thus, in the English Language course, essential factors to develop the learning of a new language were lost, making the teaching insufficient to retain knowledge and provide greater linguistic interaction in the target language.

It is also understandable the importance of Digital Literacy to achieve the full potential of the platforms used and thus to be able to provide lessons and activities compatible with the context in which they fit, in an adapted, dynamic, interactive and attractive way. It is noticeable the importance of the effective use of digital platforms and of the knowledge of how the elements that compose them work. Thus, four platforms widely used in English Language classes during the remote teaching period were analyzed.

It was possible to conclude that the platforms can integrate functions that help teachers to make their classes and proposed exercises more dynamic. In addition, they can work as satisfactory resources to improve the teaching of English in both digital and face-to-face environments. Therefore, platforms are a great way to present a more complete, communicative, and varied class that can rely on interactive audiovisual media, activating not only its linguistic skills but its capacity of requiring an example, an immersive experience, motivation, activities, or other ability that the context needs for the students.

The digital platforms, as much as they present satisfactory elements for presenting an interactive and motivating lesson or activity, are nothing more than resources that need to be manipulated by properly prepared and literate professionals, and are available to assist the teacher in whatever is necessary:

[...] and the teacher keep in mind that they should not privilege any technological resource or any kind of teaching support material to the detriment of himself. It is necessary, considering that and above all, to trust the human element, because the human resource is still the main resource in the teaching process. (BELÉM; GUIMARÃES, 2020, p. 02)

Therefore, the teacher remains the main manager of the classroom, who knows how to choose, adapt, and operate the tools according to each class, subject and context. One should also consider that despite the important resources that the platforms provide, face-to-face classes are still more complete and essential than remote classes, but these technologies can always be adjusted to face-to-face teaching, adding even more to offline classes.

The use of remote teaching in the pandemic context had its advantages, but it is necessary to consider the disadvantages of emergency teaching. Besides the health situation that everyone was going through, communication with technology also presented problems that were difficult to control, students and teachers faced financial situation and could not afford to buy tools for the classes, it was necessary minimal social contact, intensive and extensive use of screens, there was a change of school environment, and a lack of knowledge about the technologies used.

The pandemic is not a favorable situation. Even though it has brought us some lessons in education, it is still a worrying public health situation. Although we have discussed about the lack of literacy and adequate adaptation being the problems for not achieving a dynamic and attractive remote classroom, it is necessary to consider that problems with the internet, personal problems, especially in the face of the pandemic context, institutional problems, adaptation problems, and the situation itself also influence the lessons to be unproductive. Nonetheless, the focus of this work was the positive effect that digital literacy and platforms bring to remote teaching.

References

ADAPTAÇÃO. In: DICIO, **Dicionário Online de Português**. Porto: 7Graus, 2022. Disponível em: <https://www.dicio.com.br/adaptacao/>. Acesso em: 19. set. 2022.

BELÉM, B. de C.; GUIMARÃES, L. P. S. **Youtube**: Recurso Tecnológico de Apoio ao Ensino e Aprendizagem para Aulas de Língua Inglesa. CONGRESSO INTERNACIONAL DE LINGUAGEM E TECNOLOGIA ONLINE, 14, 2020, Belo Horizonte. Anais... Belo Horizonte: UFMG, p. 1-7, 2020. Disponível em: http://www.periodicos.letras.ufmg.br/index.php/anais_linguagem_tecnologia/article/view/17702. Acesso em: 22 set. 2022.

CARVALHO, L. A. de. *et al.* **O uso do padlet na aprendizagem da Língua Inglesa:** um relato de experiências WORKSHOP DE INFORMÁTICA NA ESCOLA, 26, 2020, Porto Alegre. Anais... Porto Alegre: Sociedade Brasileira de Computação, p. 161-169, 2020. Disponível em: <https://sol.sbc.org.br/index.php/wie/article/view/12608>. Acesso em: 26 set. 2022

DIRGRAD, CEFET - MG. **Perguntas e Respostas sobre o Ensino Remoto Emergencial (ERE).** Minas Gerais: CEFET, 2021. Disponível em: <https://www.dirgrad.cefetmg.br/ensino-remoto-emergencial-ere/perguntas-e-respostas-sobre-ere/#:~:text=S%C3%A3o%20estrat%C3%A9gias%20did%C3%A1ticas%20e%20pedag%C3%B3gicas,c%20comunidade%20escolar%20durante%20a%20pandemia>. Acesso em: 22 set. 2022.

FAIER, G. S. **A Contribuição das Metodologias Ativas para a Prática Oral da Língua Inglesa em Meio Remoto.** CONGRESSO NACIONAL DE EDUCAÇÃO, 7, 2021, João Pessoa. Anais... João pessoa: Realize, p. 1-12, 2021. Disponível em: https://editorarealize.com.br/editora/anais/conedu/2021/TRABALHO_EV150_MD1_SA119_ID3760_15102021123322.pdf. Acesso em: 19 set. 2022.

KOBS, T. S.; BETTONI, M. A pronúncia do inglês em canais do YouTube especializados em ensino de língua inglesa para brasileiros. **Research, Society and Development**, v.11, n.5, p.1-12, 2022. Disponível em: <https://pdfs.semanticscholar.org/7fo2/167df2d285fac73245c6b0381b76e606006b.pdf>. Acesso em: 25 set. 2022.

LEMOS, M. S. C.; A plataforma Google Forms como possibilidade de Protótipo de Ensino. **Línguatec**, v.7, n.1, p.195-209, 2022. Disponível em: <https://periodicos.ifrs.edu.br/index.php/LinguaTec/article/view/5523/3111>. Acesso em: 28 set. 2022.

LIMA, G. S.; FERNANDES, P. M. Uma Análise da Experiência de Criação de Material Didático para o Ensino de Língua Inglesa Utilizando Vídeos do Youtube e Netflix em Aulas de Conversação. **Ribanceira**, n.19, p.21-39, 2019. Disponível em: <https://periodicos.uepa.br/index.php/ribanceira/article/view/3287>. Acesso em: 23 set. 2022.

OLIVEIRA, L. C. **Análise de materiais didáticos de língua inglesa, elaborados por professores em formação inicial, sob a ótica da multimodalidade.** 2021. 202 f. Tese (Doutorado em Linguística) – Centro de Humanidades, Universidade Federal do Ceará, Fortaleza, 2021. Disponível em: <https://repositorio.ufc.br/handle/riufc/62080>. Acesso em: 19 set. 2022.

OLIVEIRA, A. S. *et al.* Ensino da Língua Inglesa em Tempos de Ensino Remoto. **Revista Ibero-Americana de Humanidades, Ciências e Educação**, v.8, n.3, p.1583-1593, 2022. Disponível em: <https://periodicorease.pro.br/rease/article/download/4746/1811/7082>. Acesso em: 19 set. 2022.

SEGATY, K.; BAILER, C. O ensino de língua inglesa na educação básica em tempos de pandemia: um relato de experiência em um programa bilíngue em implantação. **Signo**, v.46, n.85, p.253-262, 2021. Disponível em: <https://online.unisc.br/seer/index.php/signo/article/view/15709>. Acesso em: 19 set. 2022.

SILVA, E. A. P.; ALVES, D. L. R.; FERNANDES, M. N. O Papel do Professor e o Uso das Tecnologias Educacionais em Tempos de Pandemia. **Cenas Educacionais**, v.4, n.10740, p.1-17, 2021. Disponível em: <https://revistas.uneb.br/index.php/cenaseducacionais/article/view/10740/7765>. Acesso em: 13 maio 2023.

SILVA, M. A.; CARVALHO JUNIOR, I. D. de. Youtube como Rede Social: Contribuições da Plataforma para a Aprendizagem de Língua Inglesa. **Percursos Linguísticos**, v.10, n.24, p.126-147, 2020. Disponível em: <https://periodicos.ufes.br/percursos/article/view/28964>. Acesso em: 23 set. 2022

SILVA, S. P. Letramento Digital e Formação de Professores na Era da Web 2.0: o que, como e por que ensinar? **Hipertextus**, v.8, n.8, p.1-13, 2012. Disponível em: <http://arquivohipertextus.epizy.com/volume8/01-Hipertextus-Vol8-Solimar-Patriota-Silva.pdf>. Acesso em: 22 set. 2022.

PEREIRA FILHO, S. A.; FRANCO, B. A. R. Ensino de língua estrangeira e a tecnologia: kahoot! quizlet e wordwall. **Brazilian Journal of Development**, v.7, n.4, p.35083-35102, 2021. Disponível em: <https://brazilianjournals.com/ojs/index.php/BRJD/article/view/27726>. Acesso em: 28 set. 2022.